

ISic0583

Italici honour a Roman (?Scipio)

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

breccia

Object

base

Editor

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2019-07-23 - Jonathan Prag revised the file based upon preparation of 2017 edition

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

First reported by Antonio Agustín, c.1559 (Prestianni Giallombardo 1993a: 182 with Tav.1) as being 'fra Tusa et Petineo et la mota di Fermo et la abadia di S.ta Maria delli Palazi alla croce'; Gualtherus (1624) described it as 'ara crucis signo

supposita bis-denis circiter passibus à templo recedens.' It remains unclear exactly what this implies, whether at a cross standing at a crossroads immediately to the north of the site (and so in re-use there)

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Castelli described the stone as “una gran base di pietra con macchie rosse e bianche” (1753: 150), and claimed to have studied it himself in 1744. Such a description implies the red/white breccia of San Marco d'Alunzio, of which several pieces can be found among the ancient material immediately outside the mediaeval church on the site today. No further description or dimensions are recorded.

Dimensions

Height unknown cm

Width unknown cm

Depth unknown cm

Layout

Both Castelli and Gualtherus note that the stone had suffered significant damage to the letters. Agustín and Gualtherus report a continuous text with no gaps, but Castelli suggests that two whole lines are missing both before and after the third surviving line of text.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

No reliable description of the letter forms is preserved.

Letter heights:

Line 1: unknown mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: unknown mm

Text

1. Italicei
2. L(ucium) Cornelium Sc[ip]i[one]m
3. honoris caussa

Apparatus

Text of CIL

Translation (en)

The Italic (honour/dedicate) Lucius Cornelius Scipio, for the sake of honour

Commentary

Both Castelli and Gualtherus note that the stone had suffered significant damage to the letters. Agustín and Gualtherus report a continuous text with no gaps, but Castelli suggests that two whole lines are missing both before and after the third surviving line of text. Editors from Mommsen onwards have suggested emending the impossible SCHIZIAM or SC FIIZIVM of the earlier editors to Scipionem, and have then speculated that this refers to L. Cornelius Scipio (Asiagenus), who was praetor in Sicily in 193 BC (see Brennan, T.C. 2000. *The Praetorship in the Roman Republic* (Oxford), 484 and 838 n.55). If lines are missing after the name, these presumably made reference to the office(s) held by the individual. Inscriptions set up outside Italy by Italici, i.e. Italians resident abroad (usually engaged in commercial activity and often described as negotiatores, i.e. 'businessmen') in honour of Roman magistrates are common in the second and first century BC, particularly in the Greek East (e.g. at Delos). The text aligns itself with other examples of the type in using the Greek construction of accusative for the honorand (Latin would normally use a dative; on such texts, including this example, see Adams, J.N. 2003. *Bilingualism and the Latin Language* (Cambridge), at 649-663). If the emendation and identification in this text is correct, then it constitutes the earliest known example of such a text, and is important evidence for early Italian presence in northern Sicily (cf. Fraschetti, A. 1981. *Per una prospografia dello sfruttamento: romani e italici in Sicilia (212 - 44 a.c.)*. In A. Giardina and A. Schiavone (eds), *Società romana e produzione schiavistica: l'italia: insediamenti e forme economiche*. Rome, Bari: 51-77; and Facella 2006: 204-208). The text also offers an early example of the gemination of the consonant in Latin (caussa).

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Ex aere

307

ΘΕΟΙΣ ΠΑΤΡΙ
 ΟΥΤΡΑΤΙΟΠΙΟ . . ΜΕΝ
 ΕΝΕΙΩΝΙ
 ΕΚΙΩΝΕΩΟΙΜΑΝ
 ΤΩΝ Ε . Υ . ΒΟΝΗΕΤΗ
 ΜΕΝ ΤΩ ΠΙ
 ΗΡΑΚΛΙΟΝ . . ΤΟ ΔΕ ΠΟΥ
 ΚΑΙ
 ΧΙΛΑΡΧΕΑΝ . . ΕΝΕΡΥΚΙ
 Ν ΕΚΕΝ

*Ara Crani fide suspensa his diebus rick-
 ter passibus à templo recedens. Lapidem ruben-
 telius & alibi creditur esse neglecte à Na-
 rura confectum. Quod si cum eis hiatum, tarde
 littere apparent, & qua arte sunt. Natura
 esse videtur. Nunc illas non nisi à feliciter
 hinc loci arcibus eductas investigant, cum
 quippe talis suis radijs simulacra impederent.
 Præter ista litteras abstrusas esse persuasivas*

IOI ITALICI
 L. CORNELIUM . SCHIZIAM
 HONORIS . CAUSA

In fastigio eiusdem are

M. LEMERICVS M F
 FAE . RVIVS
 V. SIBI . ET . MELVIAE . ARVIAE
 VXORI . SVAE

In aditu ad

. . ΝΟΝ ΤΑΝΙΕΡΟ . . (184)
 ΠΟΥΕΝΕΟΧ ΑΑΗΡΩΝΑ Διογενει F. Λατινο-
 ΕΝ ΚΑΙ ΕΤΕΡΤΕΙΩΝ ΑΝΤΙΣΤΡΟΦΩΝ

S. PHILADELPHVS
 opidum Iuliae Larcæ & Spataforæ

In aede maiori 304 ΟΧΕΙΑΣ Οχίαιας

Iuxta campum S. Nicolai

305 ΣΟΧΙΑΘΑΙΣ

*II. lapide à S. Fratello, in via Masfa-
 rini, in fundo Terr. de Cortia*

306 ΟΧΕΙΑΜΟΤ Chedami F.

*In Monte parvi sacellum SS. Fratrum
 in marmore*

307

ΟΔΑΜΟΣ
 ΑΝΔΡΩΝΑ ΟΡΑΧΙΟΥ Μ Ε
 ΕΥΕΡΤΕΧΙΑΣ ΕΝΕΚΕΝ
 ΘΕΟΙΣ ΠΑΤΡΙ

Popular
 Andream Orarij F.
 benevolentiae causa
 Deo annuhat

SANCTVS . MARCVS

Comitatus Vine. Iosephi Filingeri

*In B. Maria Nivali. in fine praegravibus
 marmoreis*

308

LIVIAE & AVGVSTI
 D E A E
 ΜΥΝΙCΙΠΙΥΜ

In sala dicitur profecta

309

.
 I . T . F .
 . . . Δ ΠΕQ . SVA .

*In pariete prope
 No. LXXXIII*

ΟΞΙΩΝΟΣ
 Οξίωνας

In castris Capucinarum ad marem

311 D . S . F . MIRON .
 D . IVNIO . D . L .
 ΟΡΙΑΙΟ . .
 E . MIRONIA . D . .

copy of 2nd edition of Gualtherus